

Climate Change Rating of OECD Countries 2021

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Abstract

This work is related to the Climate Change Rating of Countries (CCR). The parameters included in the rating are CO₂ emissions per capita and per GDP, cumulative CO₂ emissions in the last 30 years, and change in the emissions in the last 10 years. The parameters are compared to the world averages.

OECD CCR is 111, 4% worse than in 2020 and 10% worse than the world average in 2021. The OECD CCR Label in 2021 is F = Red.

OECD moved down from position 153 to 159 (the world position is equivalent to 146), out of a total of 208.

3 OECD countries in Group G are responsible for 50% of the total OECD CO₂ emissions in 2021. The average CCR of Group G is 60% above the world CCR in 2021.

Keywords:

Climate Change, Global Warming, CO₂ emissions, CO₂ per capita, CO₂ per GDP, CO₂ emissions per capita, CO₂ emissions per GDP, Climate Change Rating, Global Warming of countries, OECD, climate justice, carbon justice

Glossary

\$\$GDP	\$2017 of cumulative GDP in the last 30 years
Ave	average
CCO2	global cumulative CO2 emissions according to publication [3], CO2 emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included, tCO2
CCp\$\$	country's cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period
CCp\$\$W	weight of parameter CCp\$\$
CCR	Climate Change Rating of countries according to this work
CGP	Conservative Global Parameter, decreasing only world parameter applied to the CCR
CO2	emissions of Carbon Dioxide, CO ₂
Cp\$	country's CO2 emissions per GDP in the last year, tCO2/\$GDP (ton CO2 per year, per \$GDP 2017 per year)
Cp\$10	country's change in Cp\$ in last 10 years, tCO2/\$GDP
Cp\$10W	weight of parameter Cp\$10
Cp\$W	weight of parameter Cp\$
CpC	country's CO2 emissions per capita in the last year, tCO2/y,cap
CpC10	country's change in CpC in last 10 years, tCO2/y,cap
CpC10W	weight of parameter CpC10
CpCW	weight of parameter CpC
EPC	Economic Power of the Country = GDP multiplied by population
GDP	Gross Domestic Product, constant international \$ 2017, \$GDP/y
Global Warming	global surface temperature change over land+ocean above 1850-1900 baseline, °C
OWID	Our World in Data – Internet site [3]

tCO ₂	metric ton of CO ₂
tCCO ₂	metric ton of cumulative CO ₂ in the last 30 y
tCO ₂ /y,cap	metric ton of CO ₂ per year, per capita
WB	World Bank
WCCp\$\$	world cumulative CO ₂ emissions in last 30 years per cumulative GDP, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
WCp\$	world CO ₂ emissions per GDP in the last year, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
WCp\$10	world change in Cp\$ in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
WCpC	world CO ₂ emissions per capita in the last year, tCO ₂ /y,cap
WCpC10	world change in CpC in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /y,cap

Climate Change Rating of Countries

Climate Change Rating of Countries (CCR) was introduced in the publication [1]. The parameters included in the rating are CO₂ emissions per capita and per GDP, cumulative CO₂ emissions in the last 30 years, and change in the last 10 years. The parameters are compared to the world averages. The rating is related to the CO₂ intensity, lower CO₂ emissions result in a lower CCR value and better rating. Climate Change Rating of Countries for 2021 is described in publication [3].

Parameters Included in the Rating

Table 1 - Parameters included in the rating

Parameter	Country Symbol	World Symbol	Unit
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	WCCp\$\$	tCO2/\$GDP
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CPC10	WCPC10	tCO2/y,cap
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	CP\$10	WCP\$10	tCO2/\$GDP

Weights of the CCR Parameters

Table 2 - CCR parameters weight

Parameter	Parameter Symbol	Weight	Weight Symbol
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	20%	CCp\$\$W
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	25%	CpCW
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	25%	Cp\$W
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	15%	CpC10W
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	Cp\$10	15%	Cp\$10W
Σ		100%	

World CCR in 2021

Table 3 - World data for 2021 [3]

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	World 2021
CO2 emissions in 2021		tCO2/y	36,102,149,000
GDP		\$GDP/y	134,535,410,379,137
Population			7,909,295,104
Cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years		tCCO2	877,679,431,339
Cumulative GDP in the last 30 years		\$\$GDP	2,672,915,852,133,670
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WCCp\$\$	tCCO2/\$\$GDP	0.000328
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.56
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000268
CpC before 10 years		tCO2/y,cap	4.72
Cp\$ before 10 years		tCO2/\$GDP	0.000331
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	97%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	81%

Table 4 - World CCR in 2021

Parameter	Parameter Symbol	Value	Weight	Index
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	100%	20%	20%
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	104%	25%	26%
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	100%	25%	25%
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	102%	15%	15%
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	Cp\$10	100%	15%	15%
Σ			100%	101.38%

The CCR rating of the world for 2021 is 101.

The world position on the countries list is equivalent to 146 (out of 208).

Table 5 - Conservative Global Parameters - CGP 2021 [3]

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	World 2021	CGP2020	CGP2021
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WCcp\$\$	tCO2/\$\$GDP	0.000328	0.000333601	0.00032836029
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.564522	4.377744993	4.37774499292
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000268	0.000270852	0.00026834682
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	96.73%	94.7266588%	94.726658766%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	81.06%	81.4770622%	81.060836832%

Rating A-G

Rating A-G includes 7 groups.

The A-G rating groups are according to the rating limits. The best rating (A) is for the lowest CCR.

Table 6 - A-G Labels (groups)

Rating	min CCR	max CCR	Color
A		57	Light Green
B	58	68	Dark Green
C	69	77	Light Blue
D	78	89	Dark Blue
E	90	105	Violet
F	106	150	Red
G	151		Black

OECD and the World

Table 7 - OECD and the world in 2021

2020	World	OECD	Share	Δ
countries	208	38	18%	
population	7,840,952,832	1,370,360,741	17%	
GDP, M\$	126,732,220	58,292,208	46%	
CO2 emissions, tCO2/y	34,325,692,000	11,251,383,490	33%	
population/country	37,696,889	36,062,125		-4%
GDP/country, M\$	609,290	1,534,005		+152%
GDP/capita, \$	16,163	42,538		+163%
CO2/country	165,027,365	296,089,039		+79%
CO2/capita	4.4	8.2		+88%
CO2/GDP, tCO2/M\$	271	193		-29%

Table 8 - OECD and the World in 2021

2021	World	OECD	Share	Δ
Countries	208	38	18%	
Population	7,909,295,104	1,373,941,940	17%	
GDP, M\$	134,535,410	61,578,608	46%	
CO2 emissions, tCO2/y	36,102,149,000	11,824,402,790	33%	
population/country	38,025,457	36,156,367		-5%
GDP/country, M\$	646,805	1,620,490		+151%
GDP/capita, \$	17,010	44,819		+163%
CO2/country	173,568,024	311,168,494		+79%
CO2/capita	4.6	8.6		+89%
CO2/GDP, tCO2/M\$	268	192		-28%

Table 9 - Change in CO2 emissions per capita

	World	OECD	Δ
CpC 2020	4.4	8.2	+88%
CpC 2021	4.6	8.6	+89%
Δ	+4%	+5%	+13%

Table 10 - Change in CO2 emissions per GDP

	World	OECD	Δ
Cp\$ 2020, tCO2/M\$	270.9	193.0	-29%
Cp\$ 2021, tCO2/M\$	268.3	192.0	-28%
Δ	-0.9%	-0.5%	-44%

OECD CpC index (CO2 emissions per capita) increased in 2021 - 13% above the world increase and the OECD Cp\$ index (CO2 emissions per GDP) decreased less than the world Cp\$ index.

Climate Change Rating of OECD Countries

Table 11 - OECD data for 2021 [3]

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	OECD	CGP	OECD
					to CGP
CO2 emissions in 2021	CO2	tCO2/y	11,824,402,790		
GDP	GDP	\$GDP/y	61,578,608,123,171		
Population			1,373,941,940		
Cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years	CCO2	tCCO2	391,513,752,590		
Cumulative GDP in the last 30 years	ΣGDP	\$GDP	1,442,910,632,329,330		
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	tCCO2/\$GDP	0.000271	0.000328	83%
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	tCO2/y,cap	8.606	4.377745	197%
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000192	0.000268	72%
CpC before 10 years		tCO2/y,cap	10.174		
Cp\$ before 10 years		tCO2/\$GDP	0.000255		
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	84.59%	94.73%	89.30%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	75.39%	81.06%	93.00%

Table 12 - OECD CCR Rating 2021

Parameter	Parameter	Value	Weight	Index
	Symbol			
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	83%	20%	17%
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	197%	25%	49%
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	72%	25%	18%
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	89%	15%	13%
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	Cp\$10	93%	15%	14%
Σ			100%	110.91%

OECD CCR is 111, 10 points behind the world average.

The OECD CCR Label in 2021 is F = Red.

OECD's position on the countries list is equivalent to 159 (the world position is equivalent to 146), out of a total of 208.

Table 13 - OECD countries below and above the world CCR

	Countries	tCO2/y
OECD countries CCR<World	26	31%
OECD countries CCR>World	12	69%

CO2 emissions of 26 OECD countries with better than the world CCR rating, are 31% of the total OECD CO2 emissions in 2021.

CO2 emissions of 12 OECD countries with worse than the world CCR rating, are 69% of the total OECD emissions.

Table 14 - OECD A-G groups in 2021

Rating	Ave CCR	tCO2/y	%	countries 2021
A	none	0	0%	0
B	55.0	78,600,410	1%	3
C	66.2	121,280,200	1%	2
D	78.3	1,861,740,940	16%	11
E	90.3	881,500,680	7%	9
F	115.2	2,937,149,560	25%	10
G	161.3	5,944,131,000	50%	3

3 OECD countries in Group G are responsible for 50% of the total OECD CO2 emissions in 2021. The average CCR of Group G is 60% above the world CCR in 2021.

Table 15 - Group A

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
A	0	#DIV/0!	List #	0
None				

Table 16 - Group B

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
B	3	55	List #	78,600,410
CRI	Costa Rica	51	10	7,819,510
SWE	Sweden	54	22	35,849,200
CHE	Switzerland	59	36	34,931,700

Table 17 - Group C

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
C	2	66	List #	121,280,200
COL	Colombia	64	45	91,703,300
DNK	Denmark	68	56	29,576,900

Table 18 - Group D

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
D	11	78	List #	1,861,740,940
PRT	Portugal	71	61	40,797,200
MEX	Mexico	73	64	407,206,000
FRA	France	73	66	305,963,000
LVA	Latvia	74	73	7,266,240
GBR	United Kingdom	75	78	346,775,000
ESP	Spain	79	89	233,650,000
ITA	Italy	82	99	328,687,000
LTU	Lithuania	83	102	13,880,900
IRL	Ireland	83	103	37,540,100
ISR	Israel	83	107	54,528,500
CHL	Chile	84	109	85,447,000

Table 19 - Group E

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
E	9	90	List #	881,500,680
HUN	Hungary	86	112	48,454,700
GRC	Greece	86	114	56,309,200
SVN	Slovenia	86	115	12,549,380
FIN	Finland	89	118	37,602,300
TUR	Turkey	91	124	446,205,000
NOR	Norway	91	125	40,918,600
NZL	New Zealand	92	129	33,789,800
AUT	Austria	94	131	64,625,700
NLD	Netherlands	98	139	141,046,000

Table 20 - Group F

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
F	10	115	List #	2,937,149,560
DEU	Germany	101	145	674,754,000
SVK	Slovakia	104	151	35,308,000
BEL	Belgium	105	152	95,722,000
ISL	Iceland	108	154	3,374,960
EST	Estonia	111	159	10,449,000
JPN	Japan	112	161	1,067,396,000
LUX	Luxembourg	118	163	8,354,600
CZE	Czechia	123	169	97,137,000
POL	Poland	126	171	328,579,000
KOR	South Korea	143	179	616,075,000

Table 21 - Group G

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO ₂ /y
G	3	161	List #	5,944,131,000
USA	United States	155	180	5,007,310,000
CAN	Canada	162	184	545,635,000
AUS	Australia	167	187	391,186,000

Changes in OECD Countries CCR Rating 2020-21

Table 22 - Changes in the number of OECD countries in CCR groups 2020-21

Rating	countries 2020	countries 2021	Δ
A	1	0	-1
B	2	3	+1
C	4	2	-2
D	8	11	+3
E	13	9	-4
F	8	10	+2
G	2	3	+1

Table 23 - Changes in OECD CO₂ emissions in CCR groups 2020-21

Rating	tCO ₂ /y 2020	tCO ₂ /y 2021	Δ
A	7,081,740	0	-100%
B	70,755,800	78,600,410	+11%
C	400,833,820	121,280,200	-70%
D	1,371,481,700	1,861,740,940	+36%
E	1,694,730,060	881,500,680	-48%
F	6,771,714,370	2,937,149,560	-57%
G	934,786,000	5,944,131,000	+536%

Climate Change Rating Results on the Website

The Climate Change Rating Results are available on the website [4].

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